

TRAFFIC PERFORMANCE COMPARISON OF CDMA AND FDMA ON CELLULAR NETWORK

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ABSTRACT

This paper provides the traffic performance comparison of CDMA and FDMA in a cellular network. With the ever increasing demand for fast internet access, multimedia services and other data based services, the need for larger network and bandwidth capability cannot be over-emphasized. These services involves either CDMA or FDMA, hence the need for this comparison. We derived Erlang capacity “formulas” for the CDMA and FDMA cellular system and a MATLAB simulation was carried out using the formulas. The results showed that the total number of Erlang of traffic that a CDMA sector can service is about 32 times that of an FDMA sector and that the total number of Erlang of traffic that a CDMA sector can service in a cellular network is about 3½ times that of an FDMA sector. The result of the analysis showed that variation in network parameters affects CDMA capacity and that CDMA has a huge capacity advantage over FDMA.

INTRODUCTION

With the ever increasing demand for very fast internet and other multimedia services, there is need for capacity analysis of frequency division multiple access (FDMA) and code division multiple access (CDMA) techniques in telecommunication networks.

Code division multiple access and frequency division multiple access are two multiple access techniques in telecommunication networks. However, there are other multiple access techniques in telecommunication networks; some of which are time division multiple access techniques, time-random multiple access technique, etc.

FDMA has a fixed number of channels while the CDMA does not have a fixed number of channels. This is because the capacity (allowable number of users) depends on the degree of interference that the network experience. Thus the capacity of a CDMA is not hard limited but interference limited. This is because blocking of subscribers making calls occur when the reverse link multiple access interference power reaches a pre-determined level that is set to maintain a certain level of signal quality [Lee and Miller, 1998]. For instance, when the interference level at a base station receiver exceeds a set of defined threshold ($z > z_0$), the system blocks (denies access) to the next user who attempts to make a call.

It is important to note that the number of users for which the CDMA blocking probability equals a certain quality of service is defined as the Erlang capacity of the system and is related to an equivalent number of channels in an FDMA cellular communication network.

Thus a CDMA blocking formula of the form:

$$B_{CDMA} = Q \left(\frac{a - b\overline{M}}{\sqrt{c\overline{M}}} \right) \dots \dots \dots \dots \dots \dots \dots \dots 1$$

is developed where \overline{M} is the Erlang capacity of the CDMA system. Substituting \overline{M} obtained from the CDMA formula above into Erlang B formula which is often applied in FDMA network, given by

$$B = P_\lambda = \frac{\frac{A^N}{N!}}{\sum_{K=0}^N \frac{AK}{K!}} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad 2$$

And can be expressed as thus:

$$B_{CDMA} = \frac{\left(\frac{\bar{M}}{N!}\right)^N}{\sum_{i=0}^n \frac{(\bar{M})^n}{n!}} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad 3$$

The above expression can be used to find the equivalent number of channels, N, to be compared with the FDMA systems.

It is important to note that the number of users (call traffic) at a given time is random, and the interference power from a user is a random variable, the probability of blocking leads to an estimate of the average number of active users that is termed the Erlang capacity of the CDMA which is to be compared with its equivalent in the FDMA cellular communication network.

The calculation and determination of Erlang capacity depends on the assumptions about the probability distribution of the cellular communication network and user interference. There is therefore the need for network operators to have a well-researched tools or models that will assist in designing networks that will ensure maximization of resources while delivering services to users with acceptable quality of service.

The objective of this paper is to develop a mathematical model of the CDMA and FDMA techniques, and analyze the traffic performance of CDMA and FDMA on cellular communication networks. In this paper a much less complex and unambiguous interference characterization is employed to give a basis for the capacity modeling of CDMA, with the reverse link interference characterization being the focus of the study.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Multiple access technique can be defined as a method that implements a connection between two points through a channel that can be shared by multiple users at different locations. This principle is almost similar to the multiplexing and demultiplexing techniques, but multiple access technique is more efficient in radio frequency (RF) than multiplexing technique because the users are always in different locations and directions.

According to Cooper *et al* (1978), the interference analysis in terms of signal to interference ratio is applicable to direct sequence systems. The assumed propagation model coupled with power control leads to a simple expression for interference at the desired base station from a point with known position in the network.

The total interference from a cell other than the desired one is calculated by integrating the interference expression mixed with a continuous and uniform user density over a circular region approximating a hexagonal cell. An analytical result is possible only for restricted values of the path loss exponent (PLE) and so the writer uses numerical integration to calculate the interference levels. The overall or total other cell interference results from the summation of all interfering cells apart from the desired one. The paper is detailed, but did not deal with the randomness of the user locations and is equivalent to calculating expected values when each user is independently and uniformly distributed over the cell of concern.

Kim K.I. (1993) did a similar analysis as above though with the exception that the fixing of the PLE at 4 leads to analytical expressions for the interference from other circular cells. This was extended to analytic expressions for the interference from the circulation cells. This is extended to an analytic result for variance.

An extension of the work of Cooper *et al* (1978) includes the effect of shadowing and voice activity monitoring was carried out by Gillhanson and Fapojuwo (1991). According to Gillhanson and Fapojuwo (1991), a standard hexagonal cellular layout is assumed with the propagation model. Also Kohno *et al*, (1995) wrote on the use of lognormal shadowing taken to be dependent on distinct paths. The total interference at a target base station (BS) is examined assuming there are equal numbers of users per cell, spread evenly and continuously.

If a base station is the target, then the interference is the fixed, constant power specified by the power control. Otherwise the interference is lognormal random variable with beam dependent on the position of the MS. To simplify the analysis an MS decides between the closest BS and the target BS only. An expression for the interference dependent upon the MS position is then multiplied by the user density (not a probability function) and integrated over the network to give the total cell interference. This total interference is a random variable due to the lognormal shadowing. Its mean and standard deviation can be calculated numerically as a function of user density. With the probability density function approximating as Gaussian, while the other cell interference is fully characterized.

A further review of the reverse link analysis of the work by Gillhansan and Fapojuwo (1991) was carried out by Viterbi *et al.* (1994), which showed that the propagation model is extended to take into consideration the dependence of the shadowing from a mobile station (MS) to different base stations (BS). Secondly, rather than choosing between the target BS and the closed BS. An MS can connect to any of the nearest mobile stations; this involves a fairly straight forward extension of the analysis in the paper by Gilhansan and Fapojuwo (1991). Although the computational complexity increased considerably to the extent that only mean values for the interference are calculated.

The results showed a dramatic drop in the mean of other-cell interference from $M = 1$ to $M = 2$ for typical values of the shadowing variance, while the improvement is small for $M > 3$.

According to Rappaport (1992), there is no modeling of shadowing but more detailed and accurate versions of the work of Lee and Miller (1995) are employed. The analysis assumes circular target cell plus wedge shaped adjacent cells, this geometry allows a fairly simple investigation into the sensitivity of the-cell interference to user density profile variation. Power control is not examined and the results are all numerical.

Robert *et al.* (1996) carried out an investigation of the effect of using actual distance of users when calculating the capacity of a CDMA network. Simulations were carried out for twenty-seven cell CDMA network. The results obtained analytically from relative average interference were first simulated and verified for comparison. The simulation results showed that for a uniform user distribution, the difference in capacity determined using relative actual interference and relative average interference is too small to warrant the incursion of heavy computational load involved in the former. This discovered advantage will be exploited in the capacity analysis of this thesis. The simulation though also showed some variation in total capacity under user placements, which could not have been predicted using the average interference for non-uniform user distribution.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The method used in this paper is based on the development of the necessary equations and framework for the modeling of the traffic performance comparison of FDMA and CDMA. It is important to point out that Erlang B formula can be applied directly to the reverse links of FDMA. This is not the case for CDMA network as the number of channels is not fixed as pointed out earlier. The number of channel of CDMA network fluctuates due to the fact that the reverse link (which the capacity is dependent on) is a function of interference. Therefore, CDMA mechanism for blocking will be developed to enable application of the Erlang B theory in its capacity analysis.

Recall that blocking in a CDMA network occurs when the reverse link multiple access interference power reaches a pre-determined level that is set to maintain acceptable signal quality. Thus, if the total user interference at a base station exceeds a pre-defined threshold, the system blocks (denies access) to the next user who may attempt to make a call.

Thus, the number of users for which the CDMA blocking probability, which we shall denote as B_{CDMA} equals a certain value is defined as the Erlang capacity of the system and is related to an equivalent number of channels in an FDMA system.

The development of the probability (blocking) model for CDMA network depends on the user interference experienced. Hence, the determination of Erlang capacity depends on the assumptions about the probability distributions of the call traffic and user interference.

FDMA Traffic Characteristics of Erlang B Formula

Knowing the state probabilities we are able to find performance measures defined by state probabilities.

(1) Time Congestion: The probability that all n – channels are busy at a random point of time is equal to the proportion of time all channels are busy (time average).

Thus, the equation below is the Erlang B formula obtained for i = n (Biebuma, 2009).

$$\therefore E_n(A) = p(n) = \frac{A^n / n!}{1 + A + \frac{A^2}{2!} + \dots + \frac{A^n}{n!}} \quad 4$$

(2) Call Congestion: The probability that a random call will be lost is equal to the proportion of call attempts blocked. If we consider one time unit, we have that B = E_n(A)

$$B = \frac{\lambda \cdot p(n)}{\sum_{n=0}^m \lambda \cdot p(n)} = p(n) = E_n(A) \quad 5$$

Using the cut equation between states |i – 1| and |i|, we get;

$$Y = \sum_{i=1}^n i \cdot p(i) = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{\lambda}{u} \cdot p(i-1) = A \cdot \{1 - p(n)\}$$

$$Y = A \cdot \{1 - E_n(A)\} \quad 6$$

Where A is the offered traffic and Y is the carried traffic, Y will be less than both A and n.

It is important to note that FDMA obeys fully the Erlang B formula and there will be no need for the formulation of blocking probability as will be carried out in CDMA below.

Formulation of Blocking Probability Formula for CDMA

Considering a CDMA network with M active users, we write thus:

$$\underbrace{\alpha_{r1} P_1 + \alpha_{r2} P_2 + \dots + \alpha_{rm} P_m}_{M \text{ reverse link signals}} + \underbrace{(N_o W)_C}_{\text{Noise power}} \quad 7$$

The symbols used in the above are defined thus; α_{ri} represents random variables representing reverse link voice activity.

P_i represents the random signal powers for the M active users.

m is the number of signals and is assumed to have a Poisson distribution so that $E\{\alpha_{r1}\} = \bar{\alpha}_r = 0.4$ and $E\{\alpha_{ri}^2\} = \bar{\alpha}_r^2 = 0.31$

Further, the total power for the M active users is thus;

$$I_0^1 = I_0^1 W = \alpha_{r2} P_2 + \dots + \alpha_{rm} P_m + (N_o W)_C \quad 8$$

Dividing through by W, the equation translates thus:

$$I_0^1 = \frac{I^1}{W} = \frac{\alpha_{r1} P_1 + \alpha_{r2} P_2 + \dots + \alpha_{rm} P_m}{W} + N_o \quad 9$$

I_0^1 is the power spectral density level for the total received interference power.

Normalizing the above equation by $I_0^1 R_b$ the equation translates thus:

$$\frac{I^1}{I_0^1 R_b} = \frac{W}{R_b} = \alpha_{r1} \frac{E_{b1}}{I_0^1} + \alpha_{r2} \frac{E_{b2}}{F_0^1} + \dots + \alpha_{rm} \frac{E_{bm}}{F_0^1} + \frac{N_o}{F_0^1} + \frac{W}{R_b} \quad 10$$

Note that $P = E_b R_b$

$$\frac{W}{R_b} = z + \frac{N_0}{F_0^1} \cdot \frac{W}{R_b} = z + n \frac{W}{R_b}$$

Note also that $z = \frac{N_0}{I_0^1}$ (thermal noise)

$$z \equiv \sum_{c=1}^M \alpha_{r1} P_i = \frac{W}{R_b} (1 - \eta) \quad \dots \dots \dots \quad 11$$

$$P_i = \frac{E b i}{I_0^1} \quad \dots \dots \dots \quad 12$$

η is a parameter indicating the loading of the CDMA system.

$\frac{W}{R_b}$ is the spread-spectrum processing gain.

Assuming Z is a random variable, and that Z has been set at threshold value. In terms of the distribution of the random variable Z , the probability that the $(M + 1)$ mobile CDMA user will be blocked is the probability that Z exceeds some threshold value Z_0 as a function of a threshold value of the interference parameter η_0 .

$$\text{Thus, } B_{\text{CDMA}} = \Pr \left\{ z > z_0 = \frac{W}{R_b} (1 - \eta) \right\} \quad \dots \dots \dots \quad 13$$

$$B_{\text{CDMA}} = \Pr \left\{ \sum_{i=1}^M \alpha \frac{W}{R_b} (1 - \eta_0) \right\} \quad \dots \dots \dots \quad 14$$

Assuming a probability density function for Z , then the evaluation of B_{CDMA} is simply a matter of integrating the probability density function over the region defined by $Z > Z_0$.

$$\text{Hence, } B_{\text{CDMA}} = \int_{z_0}^{\alpha} dx p(x) \quad \dots \dots \dots \quad 15$$

The exact value of z is not known, however, an approximation is needed to compute B_{CDMA} .

The CDMA blocking probability can be expressed as:

$$B_{\text{CDMA}} = \Pr \{ Z > Z_0 \} = \Pr \left\{ \frac{Z - E(Z)}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(z)}} > \frac{Z_0 - E(Z)}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(z)}} \right\} \quad \dots \dots \dots \quad 16$$

$$B_{\text{CDMA}} = Q_Z \left(\frac{Z_0 - E(Z)}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(z)}} \right) \quad \dots \dots \dots \quad 17$$

Note that Q_z is the notation for the complementary cumulative distribution function of the standardized version of the random variable Z .

The Gaussian approximation method can be used to solve this probability model.

Gaussian Approximation Method

Based on the fact that z is a sum, that is central limit theorem, we can write

$$Q_Z(x) \times Q(x) = \int_x^{\alpha} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{-t^2/2} dt \quad \dots \dots \dots \quad 18$$

Thus, the blocking probability model can be calculated using:

$$B_{\text{CDMA}} = Q \left(\frac{Z_0 - E\{Z\}}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(z)}} \right) \quad \dots \dots \dots \quad 19$$

Using values from [Jhong *et al.*, 1998] thus;

$$y\sigma_{dB} = 2.5dB, M_{dB} = 7dB, W = 1.2277MH, R_b = 9.6kbps, X_o = 0.9, \\ \alpha_r = 0.4, \alpha_r^2 = 0.31, \beta = (\ln 10/10), P_{med} = e^{\beta md\beta}$$

Equation 35 can be reduced thus;

$$B_{CDMA} = Q \left(\frac{115.2 - 2.37 (+\zeta) \overline{M}}{3.89 \sqrt{1 + \zeta^1} \overline{M}} \right) \quad \dots \dots \dots \quad 37$$

Equation 34 is therefore, the blocking probability formula for CDMA network as a function of Erlang capacity M . S^1 can assume typical experiment value thus $S = S^1 = 0.55$.

Applying MATLAB simulation using equation 37 will provide the traffic comparison between CDMA and FDMA in cellular networks.

RESULTS

In the previous section, analysis was done on both CDMA and FDMA to evaluate capacity in terms of number of channels and subscriber capacity in a cell or sector for network planning and dimensioning. The graphical plots and analysis of CDMA using probability formula for Gaussian assumptions is used in describing the traffic comparison between advanced mobile phone services (AMPS) application in FDMA and CDMA. Below is the MATLAB plot of B_{CDMA} against the average number of users.

Figure 1: CDMA blocking probability for $M_{dB}=5dB$

Figure 2: CDMA blocking probability for $M_{dB}=6dB$

Figure 3: CDMA blocking probability for $M_{dB}=7dB$

Erlang Capacity Analysis

A plot of the CDMA blocking probability against the Erlang capacity (average number of users) is then plotted. From figure 1 above, it is obvious that at a given level of blocking, increment in the value of the number of users, M_{dB} decrease the capacity for the same probability. Let us take an example from the various graphs for explicit explanations. For $B_{cdma} = 10^{-2} = 0.01 = 1\%$.

From the figure 1, for multiple cells, the various values of the Erlang capacity are 43 and for single cell, the Erlang capacity is 50.

In figure 2, the equivalent number of channels in a CDMA system that corresponds to a value of blocking probability has been obtained. Thus, comparison of traffic on CDMA and FDMA on cellular network can be done. But for the avoidance of doubt, let's adopt the graph for $M_{dB} = 6dB$. The Erlang capacities are obtained as 32 for multiple cells and 38 for single user for $E_b/N_o = 6dB$ at $B_{cdma} = 0.01$.

Therefore, for an FDMA sector which supports 19 channels, gives 12.3 from the Erlang B table. Thus, another advantage of CDMA over FDMA is thus;

$$M_{\text{CDMA}} = 43 \text{ Erlang} / 12.3 \text{ Erlang} = 3.5.$$

This therefore indicates that the total number of Erlangs of traffic that a CDMA sector can service in a cellular network is about 3½ times that of an FDMA sector.

However, it is to be noted that this traffic performance improvement could be 30 times more if we take cognizance of the fact that in a 12.5 MHz cellular band, we can have as many as nine 1.25 MHz frequency assignments for a CDMA cellular network.

The implication of this is that the number of frequency assignments, which is nine, is multiplied by N to get the effective number of CDMA channels available in a particular sector. After this is done, the corresponding Erlang capacity can be obtained from an Erlang B formula by identifying the offered load with a multi-FA CDMA Erlang capacity denoted by $M_{\text{multi-FA}}$. The assumption here is that all the nine channels are available for assignments in the cellular network. It is also assumed that the mobile is capable of accessing any of them.

It is important to point out here, that this capacity gain in traffic requires careful implementation of sound engineering design principles that is peculiar to the spread spectrum waveform that is employed by CDMA cellular system.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

CONCLUSION

From the results obtained, it is obvious that this paper has achieved its goals. We have derived Erlang capacity “formulas” for the CDMA and FDMA cellular system under separate approximations for the interference statistics: a Gaussian approximation, by invoking the CLT. The stochastic nature of call arrivals and departures were characterized using statistical means. The interference contributed by each user was modeled as the blocking probability. The Gaussian approximation yielded a simpler result and therefore was used.

Blocking occurred when the reverse link multiple access interference power reached a predetermined level that is set to maintain acceptable signal quality. When the total user interference at a base station receiver exceeded the set threshold, the system blocked the next user attempting to place a call.

The number of users for which the CDMA blocking probability equaled 1% as chosen was taken to be the Erlang capacity of the network. Thus, a new CDMA blocking probability model is developed that enabled the estimation and analysis of Erlang capacity of CDMA networks.

Graphic results for the blocking model generated showed the effect of variations in interference parameters on CDMA capacity. The Erlang capacity from the model was adapted into Erlang B formula to estimate capacity in terms of channels, and the number of subscribers a typical CDMA sector could accommodate. The results showed that the total number of Erlang of traffic that a CDMA sector can service is about 32 times that of an FDMA sector and that the total number of Erlangs of traffic that a CDMA sector can service in a cellular network is about 3½ times that of an FDMA sector. This showed that CDMA has a huge capacity advantage over FDMA

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendation can make this paper of immense practical usefulness. Computer simulations can be incorporated into the work to produce test scenarios and results for enhanced analysis.

The model can be built into a handheld instrument that can be readily usable by network operators for planning and design.

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Received for Publication: 19/08/11

Accepted for Publication: 17/10/11

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